

2. Waveforms recorded during GLH feeding on susceptible TN1 (top) and resistant ASD7 (bottom) rice varieties using an electronic monitoring device, IIRI.

A fine (18 m μ), 5-cm-long gold wire was attached to the dorsum of an 8- to 10-h-old GLH female by silver paint. The insect was starved for 2 h and then placed on the leaf blade of a 30-d-old susceptible TN1 or resistant ASD7 rice plant. The gold wire was connected to the negative input terminal of a D. C. chart recorder. The voltage source was two 1.5 V D. C. batteries connected in a series. The

positive battery terminal was connected with the plant roots through aluminum foil and moistened filter paper (Fig. 1). The negative battery terminal was connected with the positive input terminal of the chart recorder. GLH feeding activity was monitored for 180 min at a chart speed of 1.5 cm/min.

The waveforms recorded for GLH showed distinct differences in the feeding

activity on susceptible and resistant plants (Fig. 2). On susceptible TN1, the GLH probed readily and ingested for longer durations from the phloem (Pi), although initially the insect also sucked small amounts of xylem sap (Xi). On resistant ASD7, the insect made brief and repeated probes followed by salivation and feeding mainly from the xylem. □

Yield losses of a susceptible rice variety to brown planthopper (BPH) in Korea

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We evaluated rice yield losses to BPH of susceptible and resistant rice varieties in fields in southern Korea. Susceptible

varieties were Sumjinbyeo (japonica) and Milyang 23 (Tongil hybrid). Cheongcheongbyeo, with the *Bph 1* gene for resistance, was the check variety.

Seedlings were transplanted in early Jun and grown using traditional cultural practices without insecticide application. The BPH population was recorded 55, 70, and 90 d after transplanting. Yields of each variety were compared with that of an insecticide-sprayed plot.

Sumjinbyeo and Milyang 23 had a large BPH population, but infestation on Cheongcheongbyeo remained low. Yield losses were 29.4% for Sumjinbyeo and 19.1% for Milyang 23 (see table). BPH did not affect Cheongcheongbyeo yield. □

Yield losses of BPH-susceptible and resistant rice varieties, Suweon, Korea.^a

Variety	Reaction to BPH	Insects/plant			Days to hopperburn		yield (t/ha)		Yield loss %
		55 DI	70 DI	90 DI	Initial	Complete	Insecticide free	Insecticide treated	
Sumjinbyeo (japonica)	S	0.4	47.1	503.4	99	105	4.1	5.8	29.4
Milyang 23 (tongil hybrid)	S	0.1	12.8	500.7	101	108	5.4	6.6	19.1
Cheongcheongbyeo	R	0.0	0.3	8.7	—	—	6.0	6.0	0.0

^aAv for 3 replications. DT = days after transplanting.

Field resistance to rice leaffolder

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Leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a major rice pest in the hilly region of U.P. Infestation from Aug to Oct peaks in Sep. We screened rice genotypes to identify sources of resistance.

Thirty-one entries for screening from different countries were received from IRRI. They were field screened in 1982 wet season. Forty-five-day-old seedlings

adjusted to expose 60-d-old seedlings to 12-14°C air temperature for about 30 d. They were scored for leaf discoloration using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. The F₂ segregation had

165 tolerant (score 3) plants, 380 moderately tolerant (score 5), and 185 susceptible (score 7-9) plants, a perfect 1:2:1 with a nonsignificant χ^2 , that indicated a monogenic inheritance for

leaf discoloration with incomplete dominance for green leaf color. The study is preliminary and no confirmation of the genetic ratio was done with F₃ progenies of backcross generations. □

Cold-tolerant rice variety MDU2

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Cold damage is a serious constraint to rice yields in the high-altitude zone of Tamil Nadu, where in winter, minimum temperature is 14.5 to 16.0°C. MDU2, a promising cold-tolerant rice variety, was approved by the Tamil Nadu State Varietal Release Committee in Jan 1984 for cultivation in the Cumbum Valley of Madurai district. MDU2 is a hybrid cross of C0-25 and IR8.

In station trials, MDU2 yielded 28%

Average yield^a of MDU2, Madurai, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		
	Research station trial (1)	Multilocation trials (23) ^b	Rice Coordinated Yield trials (8)
MDU2	3.7	6.1	4.4
IR20	2.9	5.5	3.7
Increase over IR20 (%)	28	11	19

^a Numbers in parentheses indicate sites from which yields were averaged. ^b Trials were conducted at the hot spot area.

more than IR20, and in 23 yield evaluation trials on farmer fields it yielded 11% more. In the rice coordinated yield trials, MDU2 yielded an average 19% more than IR20 (see table).

Spikelet sterility was 23% for MDU2 versus 45% for IR20. MDU2 is a medium-duration (130-135 d), semidwarf variety

with medium tillering ability and good panicle exertion. Grains are medium slender with white kernels, and grain type is acceptable to local consumers. It has some tolerance for leaf blight, gall midge, leafroller, and stem borer, and is recommended for cultivation in the second crop season (Oct-Feb) in the Cumbum Valley. □

Pest management and control DISEASES

Relative amount of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in an infected plant

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Scoring of rice varieties resistance to RSV has been based on percentage of infected seedlings. Using this method, it is

Reaction of extracts of Mawee and TNI infected with RSV at 30 d after inoculation. IRRI, 1984.

Relative amounts of RSV in infected rice plants on different days after inoculation, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to RSV ^a	Absorbance at 405 nm of extracts in ELISA		
		30 DAI ^b	45 DAI ^b	60 DAI ^c
Ptb 21	I	0.38 bc	0.48	0.25 ns
Murungakayan	R	0.28 c	0.64	0.32
Mawee	R	0.88 a	1.08	0.75
Balaratawee	R	0.83 a	0.93	0.56
Hathili	R	0.80 a	1.43	0.40
IR22	I	0.84 a	0.91	0.69
IR50	R	0.70 ab	0.87	0.21
TN1	S	0.78 ab	0.91	0.55
Average		0.69	0.90	0.47

^a Results of mass screening were based on 0-30% infection = R, 31-60% infection = I, 61-100% infection = S. DAI= days after inoculation. In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different. ns: not significant. ^b Average A₄₀₅ of extracts at 1:200 dilution. ^c Average A₄₀₅ of extracts at 1:160 dilution.

not clear whether the resistant varieties are resistant to RSV infection or to virus multiplication. Therefore, we determined the resistance of eight selected varieties and the relative amount of the virus in each variety by mass screening and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Seven-d-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated at five brown plant-

hoppers/seedling and then grown in the greenhouse. One month later, three infected seedlings were selected from each variety and transplanted singly in clay pots. At 30, 45, and 60 d after inoculation, extracts of the whole plant, except the root, were tested by ELISA. γ -globulin was coated with 2.5 μ g/ml and γ -globulin/alkaline phosphate conjugate was diluted 300 times. The relative